

Precision Agriculture through AI: Boosting Yields for Smallholder Farmers in the Global South.

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Abstract

Smallholder farmers in the Global South face numerous challenges, including limited resources, the impacts of climate change, and a lack of access to modern technologies. This paper explores how precision agriculture, powered by artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, can benefit these farmers, who make up a significant portion of the agricultural sector in many countries, particularly in the Global South. The paper also examines the potential of AI to promote sustainable farming practices and address some of the key challenges faced by smallholder farmers.

AI technologies, such as machine learning, can be employed in soil analysis to recommend optimal crops for planting, assist in the identification of crop diseases and suggest possible solutions, monitor crop production yields, and facilitate loan disbursement based on farm analyses. Additionally, AI-powered weather forecasts can inform farmers when to plant specific crops and estimate the time required for harvesting.

The paper argues that precision agriculture has the potential to be a game changer for smallholder farmers in the Global South, but only if it is implemented through a collaborative, ethical, and sensitive approach that addresses their unique challenges and needs.

General Terms

Algorithms, Artificial Intelligence (A.I), Global South, Precision Agriculture, Farming, Scalability.

1. Introduction

In recent years, South–South Cooperation (SSC) is increasingly recognized as an effective instrument for catalyzing economic development by fostering the exchange of innovation and good practices, and expanding market opportunities across countries with a similar level of development and shared development objectives, such as those reflected in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)(Food and Agricultural Organisation,2022).Smallholder farmers in the Global South face numerous challenges that hinder their ability to achieve optimal yield of their crops which results in improved livelihoods.Some of these challenges include limited climate challenge which has dramatically reduced harvests and left many families hungry(One Acre Fund, n.d).

Precision agriculture is a term used in modern data-driven technologies for growing crops. Compared to traditional techniques, precision agriculture has many advantages. Implementing precision technologies can play a huge role in understanding soil types, improving soil quality, making realistic crop choices, managing irrigation timing and harvest moments, monitoring and yield production. It provides an improved understanding of the spatial demands of a particular agricultural area which can be coupled with highly accurate decision support tools and early warning systems. (Climate ADAPT, 2023).

Precision technology promises to offer a promising solution to address the challenges which have been specified above. Integration of these technological practices offers solutions whereby it addresses a diverse range of challenges. It has been noted that there is better crop monitoring, reduced loss of crop yield, saving of resources such as water and energy, reduced environmental degradation and reduced lowering carbon footprint (synergy with mitigation aspects). Examples include reduced nitrate leaching in cropping systems, reduced groundwater contamination by extracting the spraying regimes and reduced erosions when precise tillage is conducted. A reduction of wasted seeds and products is also expected. Environmental benefits include reduced eutrophication (due to lower use of nutrients) and pollution (due to lower use of pesticides). (Climate ADAPT, 2023).

While precision agriculture mostly applies to large scale farmers and majority of it is implemented in developed countries, it can be implemented in developing countries or the Global South as it is now called. But the key question which should be asked is how can it be implemented. Programs from Michigan State University (MSU) led by Maredia and fellow Michigan State University researchers are overseeing the Exchanges, Training and Scholarships component, in which faculty members and students will be trained on an assortment of agricultural topics. Maredia has also identified programs from MSU that could be useful to scientists, extension specialists and farmers in developing countries. One is [PhotosynQ](#), an initiative led by David Kramer, a John A. Hannah distinguished professor and Michigan State University AgBioResearch scientist. (Michigan State University September 30 2019).

2. Related Work

Agriculture plays a very important role in an economy. It is the backbone of certain countries case in point Kenya. According to a survey done by the Central Bank of Kenya, agriculture contributed 20 percent of Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The sector also employs over 40 percent of the total population and more than 70 percent of the rural populace. (Central Bank of Kenya, 2024). Given the critical role it plays it is important to ensure that enough food is produced that meets the needs of an economy.

In regions heavily reliant on agriculture, many smallholder farms, which typically cover less than 4 hectares, struggle with accessing essential resources like irrigation and fertilizers. Compounded by a lack of advanced technologies, these farmers face difficulties in meeting the specific needs of their crops, which affects overall productivity and income (Advancing Agricultural Practices in the Global South with Amini's Precision Technology, n.d).

Traditional farming systems have been there for along time and they have played a key role when it came to feeding the population. However, there are reasons why in the long run these farming methods are not sustainable. First of all traditional methods tend to have a downside like depletion of soil nutrients, Deforestation, soil erosion, monoculture is crop specialization, when a single variation of cultivar of species is cultivated, the problem connected with this technique are compounded. Pesticide resistance caused by pests which have built a resistance towards this pesticides is usually caused by a usage of a mixture of different chemicals. Water erosion, soil salinization (excessive accumulation of water-soluble salts by plants and pollution and silt) (Concave Agri, n.d).

Precision agriculture in recent years has gotten a lot of traction when it comes to research. Different studies shows us how this type of agriculture can improve productivity, reduce loss of items, help in combating crop diseases. Application of this technology is a game changer in the agricultural sector in many ways which will be highlighted in the course of this paper. Case in point Apollo Agriculture which uses satellite imagery of farms and uses artificial intelligence to make better decisions concerning loans that can be granted to a specific farmer. This is one of many companies in Kenya that does this kind of job.

More recently, researchers have been conducting studies on the applicability of precision agriculture in the Global South more so on the smallholder farmers. (United Nation Development Program 2021) This presented opportunities that can be leveraged using this technology that is smart monitoring, weather monitoring, soil monitoring, pest surveillance and disease monitoring, precision spraying whereby this one helps in curbing air pollution by regulating the amount of pesticides sprayed on the crops and yield monitoring which is what the paper addresses mostly.

Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies like deep learning, data analytics and machine learning, Internet of Things (IOT) technologies tools like sensors are very key in enabling precision technology and making it accessible to the smallscale holder in the Global South. This technology is made possible by rapid advances in deep learning (DL) and the Internet of Things (IOT) allowing farmers to upgrade their agriculture operations to sustainably fulfill the future food supply (Science Direct June 2023).

This literary work showcases an emerging trend which explores precisions agriculture reorientational approach towards boosting yields through cost saving approaches like precision sparying and irrigation

in the Global South. Nonetheless, there are still research gaps which need to be tackled around the area of deploying artificial intelligence driven solutions to communities in the Global South. The current study aims to contribute empirical insights on implementing precision agriculture in an ethical, collaborative manner which will be very sustainable to smallholder farmers more so in the Global South.

3. Proposed Framework

So far the paper has shown that small scale farmers in the Global South face numerous challenges, which include limited resources in terms of advanced technologies, financial resources and drastic change in climatic weather conditions (International Fund for Agricultural Development, 29th November 2023). To address this challenge and increase the yields of farmers, I propose an AI-enabled precision agricultural framework specifically for smallholder farming communities in the Global South. Our style of tackling or our approach towards this issue is a proposed framework that anchors on affordable and accessible technologies like mobile devices, sensors with advanced AI techniques to provide applied insights and recommendations for optimized farm management practices.

4. Key Components and Workflow

1: Collection of Data: We utilize a network of low-cost sensors deployed in smallholder farms to collect data on soil conditions e.g. the moisture, nutrients levels, crop growth rate (for specifications this will be dependent on the type of crop as different crops have different growth stages), weather patterns of the area and size of the land (This is applicable to farmers who are accessing advanced cash for growth) an example is what Apollo Agriculture and One Acre Fund is doing. For Apollo you can purchase goods on credit whereby you apply for a loan and get an instant credit decision which is powered by Apollo's machine learning credit models. Whereas One Acre fund does asset financing to farmers. It's been noted that most farmers in the Global South still use manual way of recording their farms progress. This is highly attributed to levels of illiteracy and low numeracy in most African communities. According to the World Development Indicators database (2016), the average literacy rate of the adult population in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) was 60% in 2011. The implication is that about 40% of SSA lacks the basic literacy and numeracy skills required for everyday life. Women who are the majority of farmers in Africa account for more than 60% of the region's total illiterate population. Some countries such as Chad, Ethiopia, Mali and Niger are highly disadvantaged with illiteracy rates of higher than 60% (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2010). (African Journals Online [AJOL], 2019, Annette Kuteesa¹ * and Miriam Kyotalimye). But I believe this is

changing as time and technology is changing as well. What we intend to do is show farmers the importance of storing this information through a management system I.e through a mobile application which will have key information such as planting dates, type of crops (This assess the duration of the yield that is why it is dependent of the crop), soil performance this carries the soil nutrients and the geographic area which is very key. The geographic area helps a farmer understand which type of crop can be grown in a particular area.

2: Data Amalgamation and Bound Compilation: After data has been collected from various sources, it is studied and analyzed carefully using the standard formats so as to give a clear output. One of the formats for this is data cleaning. In data cleaning you are removing unused or redundant data. One of the key things in this process of data cleaning is to ensure that the data is clean and there is consistency. This is one of the process which takes a long time in the field of data.

3: AI-Based Technique Modelling and Analysis: Through the use of machine learning algorithms and different techniques in machine learning like computer vision techniques the amalgamated and bound data is analyzed, the platform will leverage on the following inputs:

- **Soil Samples:** AI predictive models are trained in such a way that they can classify different soil samples. This is based on historical data and also on environmental factors. For the outcome to be more accurate one needs more data which will make the results more accurate.
- **Weather Patterns:** The models are trained in such a way that they can forecast weather patterns which is also based on historical data (Visual Crossing). Visual crossing provides weather conditions of any demographic location in the world. The provided data is based on historical data which has been analysed extensively. The weather patterns also covers the geographical location of where the crops are planted.
- **Type of Water:** This is also another important factor which will be considered when doing our analysis. The type of water used also plays a big role when it comes to farming. Growing crops in salty water is different as compared to growing crops in fresh water bodies. If saline water is used in irrigation it can create a physiological drought – where the roots struggle to take water up due to the high EC and plants start wilting and die (High Sodium Soil Effect On Plant Growth – Cropnuts, n.d).
- **Farming Practices:** Different demographics have different ways of how the grow and cultivate crops. There are still places where they rely on traditional way of doing farming. However, initiatives in precision agriculture technology offer a path forward, merging traditional practices with modern tech to optimize production and sustainability. (Advancing Agricultural Practices in the Global South with Amini's Precision Technology, n.d). By considering farming practices and

educating farmers on the importance of adopting different and better ways of farming practices, there will be gradual transformation among farmers in the Global South.

- **Size of the Land:** This helps when it comes to determining the amount of resources to be deployed in a particular farm. It does not make sense to deploy resources of a four hectares on a one hectare piece of land. This is where precision technology comes in, by leveraging on the size of the land we can determine the amount of resources to be deployed. In addition to this size of the land which can also be used when a lending institution wants to provide insurance or loans to small scale farmers in the Global South. One of the companies which uses this technology is Pula Advisors (<https://www.pula-advisors.com/>). Pula uses satellite data collected over a period of time so as to be able to accomplish this critical task of offering insurance to small scale holder farmers mostly in the Global South. The company uses a variety of factors when it comes to determining the amount a farmer has to receive and size of land is one of them.
- **Crop Diseases:** Pula platform largely uses information which is image based to give remedy recommendation of a particular crop disease affecting a certain crop. It can also use words based on the input it has been given to also provide recommendation. It will also contain a consultant who will also provide the relevant feedback as machines are not one hundred percent accurate. The feedback will be relevant and applicable to the unique context of the farmer in different regions.
- **Yield Records:** To make proper and accurate yield output I recommend that past and future yields be put into consideration whereby a farmer records what he or she has gotten. From the records the farmer can determine where he or she has been losing his or her produce.
- **Crop Growth Monitoring:** In machine learning specifically computer vision, algorithms are coded in such a way that they are applied to analyze images of crops, detection of any plant issues as well as the health of the crop.

4:Recommendations: Insights gotten from the the AI-based recommendation system will be processed and an expert opinion will be provided based on an algorithm written. The recommendations will be tailored towards a particular needs of the farmer. These recommendations cover a wide base of solutions like for example best time to do planting of a particular crop, when the harvest will happen, salinity of the soil, fertilizer application that is the amount to be applied given certain parameters of the land, weather forecast and expected yield based on the crop.

5:Propagation: After the recommendations have been generated by the algorithm they are delivered to farmers via a mobile application. For mobile application this applies mostly to the ones who are

conversant with technology. There are companies which have support for Short Message Service (SMS) which can only send text-only messages up to one hundred and sixty 160 characters. One company in point is Africa's Talking (AT, <https://africastalking.com/>). Intuitive visualizations are also utilized that is interactive dashboards. To make it more inclusive there is localized language support as not everyone is well conversant with English. Case in point is by use of local languages in Artificial Intelligence (A.I), one example is Digital Umuganda (<https://digitalumuganda.com/>) an AI and open data company with a mission to enable access to information in local African languages. Digital Umuganda creates open source datasets, models and tools that make it possible for NLP including large language models to work for marginalized communities that speak under resourced languages.

5. Unique features and Innovation

The proposed Artificial Intelligence (A.I) precision technology based agricultural framework addresses an idiosyncratic challenge mostly faced by farmers in the Global South. Some of the proposed solutions include:

- **Participatory:** To make it more engaging it is highly encouraged to farmers to be engaging each other in the platform through consistent feedback. Knowledge promotion is highly encouraged among one another. The whole point is to empower communities to make adjustments and refine to better ways of farming. This will also be an opportunity for the farmers to make the framework better through active participation.
- **Scalability:** The platform which is designed and architected in a modular way allows for ease of scaling ensuring long-term sustainability and impact. Scalability can also be looked at in terms of the technological aspect, this is whereby a new person is onboarded to work with the platform it is more easier to scale the platform.
- **Affordable Technologies:** Short Message Service (SMS) works better in environments where there is low internet penetration. Through USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data) a Global system for mobile communications protocol that is used to send text messages, farmers can leverage on it by dialing a USSD (Unstructured Supplementary Service Data) code and accessing the service which they need. There is also the use of lowcost sensors and mobile devices which will be used for monitoring. Our goal is to ensure that there is accessibility of these tools to small scale holder farm in the Global South.
- **Region-Specific Modelling:** The Artificial Intelligence (A.I) models in our platform are designed in such a way that the data is specific to particular regions I.e local climate, soil conditions and farming practices of different regions. The main reason for doing this is to ensure

that the recommendations you get are tailored to the context of a particular geographical location.

6.Potential Benefits and Impact

Needless to say,there are potential benefits for the above mentioned approach or framework.For example in Nigeria farmers are encouraged to key in to the practice of precision farming so as to increase production efficiency, reduce production cost and improve the quality of crop (THE NEED FOR PRECISION AGRICULTURE IN NIGERIA, Ibrahim et al., n.d).Precision agriculture dramatically improves the efficiency of crops and saves financial costs while increasing production.However, the savings are significantly higher than with traditional agricultural methods in the long run. So, growers can accurately sum the required fertilizer amount, determine effective fertilizer types for a particular area.Moreover, the importance of precision farming technologies is that they improve the planning of agricultural operations for an extended period, adjusting the real-time strategy during force majeure.(Precision Agriculture: Technology To Boost Crop Farming, March 2024).

In addition to this, precision agriculture is helpful for farmers and the environment as well.Moreover, these areas are interconnected since environmental degradation worsens agriculture.Some of the benefits of this controlled system of agriculture include:

- Minimizing the cost of materials and resources, like water, seeds, fuel, pesticides, etc.;
- Maintaining soil health by reducing the number of pesticides;
- Lowering agricultural dependence on weather conditions;

All these advantages of precision farming allow farmers to improve the quality of products significantly and, at the same time, reduce their costs (Precision Agriculture: Technology To Boost Crop Farming, March 2024).

Through a combination of factors such as participatory approach, scalability, affordable technologies and region specific modelling this approach promises to deliver a new perspective which in the long run empowers the small scale holder farmer in the Global South.Optimizing the soil use preserves its quality, enabling a stable food supply. Therefore, precision farming in agriculture plays an essential part in solving the global problem of hunger.(Precision Agriculture: Technology To Boost Crop Farming, March 2024).This will enable the Global South to have increased crop yield and thus food security which leads to economic empowerment and development in those regions.

7.Illustrative Diagrams

7.1. What is GPS (Global Positioning System)?

It is a good thing we first take a step back and understand what this word Global Positioning System (GPS) mean and dive deeper as it will help in showing the correlation in what we are solving.

The Global Positioning System website gives a definition of Global Positioning System (GPS) as a U.S.-owned utility that provides users with positioning, navigation, and timing (PNT) services. This system consists of three segments: the space segment, the control segment, and the user segment. The U.S. Space Force develops, maintains, and operates the space and control segments

(<https://www.gps.gov/systems/gps/>).

- **Space Segment** - The Global Positioning System (GPS) space segment consists of a constellation of satellites transmitting radio signals to users. The United States is committed to maintaining the availability of at least 24 operational Global Positioning System (GPS) satellites, 95% of the time. To ensure this commitment, the U.S. Space Force has been flying 31 operational Global Positioning System (GPS) satellites for well over a decade (<https://www.gps.gov/systems/gps/space/>).
- **Control Segment** - The Global Positioning System (GPS) control segment consists of a global network of ground facilities that track the Global Positioning System (GPS) satellites, monitor their transmissions, perform analyses, and send commands and data to the constellation. The current Operational Control Segment (OCS) includes a master control station, an alternate master control station, 11 command and control antennas, and 16 monitoring sites. The locations of these facilities are shown in the map (<https://www.gps.gov/systems/gps/control/> & <https://www.gps.gov/multimedia/images/GPS-control-segment-map.pdf>)
- **User Segment** - Like the Internet, Global Positioning System (GPS) is an essential element of the global information infrastructure. The free, open, and dependable nature of Global Positioning System (GPS) has led to the development of hundreds of applications affecting every aspect of modern life. Global Positioning System (GPS) technology is now in everything from cell phones and wristwatches to bulldozers, shipping containers, and ATM's. Global Positioning System (GPS) boosts productivity across a wide swath of the economy, to include farming, construction, mining, surveying, package delivery, and logistical supply chain management. Major communications networks, banking systems, financial markets, and power grids depend heavily on Global Positioning System (GPS) for precise time synchronization. Some wireless services cannot operate without it. Global Positioning System (GPS) saves lives by preventing transportation accidents, aiding search and rescue efforts, and speeding the delivery of emergency services and disaster relief. Global Positioning System (GPS) is vital to

the Next Generation Air Transportation System (NextGen) that will enhance flight safety while increasing airspace capacity. Global Positioning System (GPS) also advances scientific aims such as weather forecasting, earthquake monitoring, and environmental protection.

Finally, Global Positioning System (GPS) remains critical to U.S. national security, and its applications are integrated into virtually every facet of U.S. military operations. Nearly all new military assets -- from vehicles to munitions -- come equipped with Global Positioning System (GPS) (<https://www.gps.gov/applications/>). This website describes just a tiny sample of existing GPS applications. New uses of Global Positioning System (GPS) are invented every day and are limited only by the human imagination.

7.2. Global Positioning System (GPS) Services

Global Positioning System (GPS) satellites provide service to civilian and military users. The civilian service is freely available to all users on a continuous, worldwide basis. The military service is available to U.S (United States) and allied armed forces as well as approved Government agencies. One of the ways the Global Positioning System (GPS) is applied to civilians is through the use precision agriculture and it is one of the main theme that is going to be covered:

7.3. Augmentation Systems

A Global Positioning System (GPS) augmentation is any system that aids by providing accuracy, integrity, availability, or any other improvement to positioning, navigation, and timing that is not inherently part of Global Positioning System (GPS) itself. A wide range of different augmentation systems have been developed by both the public and private sectors. To meet specific requirements, the U.S (United States) government has fielded a number of publicly available Global Positioning System (GPS) augmentation systems, including (but not limited to) the following systems (<https://www.gps.gov/systems/augmentations/>).

- **Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS)** - Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS), a regional space-based augmentation system (SBAS) operated by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA), supports aircraft navigation across North America. Although designed primarily for aviation users, Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS) is widely available in receivers used by other positioning, navigation, and timing communities. Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) is committed to providing Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS) service at the performance levels specified in the Global Positioning System (GPS) Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS) Performance Standard. Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) is improving Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS) to take advantage of the future GPS safety-of-life signal to provide even better performance. The Wide Area Augmentation System (WAAS) service is interoperable with other regional SBAS services, including those operated by Japan Multi-functional Satellite Augmentation

System(MSAS), European Geostationary Navigation Overlay Service (EGNOS), and India - GPS-aided GEO augmented navigation (GAGAN (<https://www.gps.gov/systems/augmentations/>)).

- **Continuously Operating Reference Stations (CORS)** - The U.S. CORS network, managed by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, archives and distributes GPS data for precise positioning tied to the National Spatial Reference System. Over 200 private, public, and academic organizations contribute data from almost 2,000 GPS tracking stations to CORS. The Online Positioning User Service (OPUS) offers free post-processing of GPS data sets to the centimeter level using CORS information. CORS is also being modernized to support real-time users.
- **Global Differential GPS (GDGPS)** - Global Differential GPS (GDGPS) is a high accuracy Global Positioning System (GPS) augmentation system developed by the NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) to support the real-time positioning, timing, and determination requirements of NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) science missions. Future NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) plans include using the Tracking and Data Relay Satellite System (TDRSS) to disseminate via satellite a real-time differential correction message. This system is referred to as the TDRSS Augmentation Service Satellites (TASS). (<https://www.gdgps.net/>)
- **International GNSS Service (IGS)** – International global navigation satellite systems (IGS) is a network of over 350 GPS monitoring stations from 200 contributing organizations in 80 countries. Its mission is to provide the highest quality data and products as the standard for global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) in support of Earth science research, multidisciplinary applications, and education, as well as to facilitate other applications benefiting society. Approximately 100 International global navigation satellite systems (IGS) stations transmit their tracking data within one hour of collection. (<http://www.igs.org/>)
- **Nationwide Differential GPS System (NDGPS)** - Nationwide Differential Global Positioning System (GPS) System (NDGPS) was a ground-based augmentation system that provided increased accuracy and integrity of GPS information to users on U.S. waterways. As of June 30, 2020, all NDGPS service has been discontinued in accordance with the NDGPS Federal Register Notice USCG-2018-

0133. With the rollout of the new GPS III satellites combined with the permanent termination of Selective Availability, DGPS is no longer deemed a necessary augmentation for close harbor approach.

- **Other Augmentations** - There are many other Global Positioning System (GPS) augmentation systems available worldwide, both government and commercial. These systems use differential, static, or real-time techniques. There are also systems that augment other global navigation satellite systems. The United States is cooperating with many other nations to ensure the interoperability of international augmentation systems with Global Positioning System (GPS) and U.S. Global Positioning System (GPS) augmentations.

7.4. The Future of Global Positioning System (GPS)

The Global Positioning System (GPS) modernization program is an ongoing, multibillion-dollar effort to upgrade the features and overall performance of the Global Positioning System. The upgraded features include new civilian and military Global Positioning System (GPS) signals. The United States (U.S) is committed to an extensive modernization program, including the implementation of a second and third civil signal on Global Positioning System (GPS) satellites. The second civil signal will improve the accuracy of the civilian service and support safety-of-life applications. The third signal will further enhance civilian capability and is primarily designed for safety-of-life applications, such as aviation. (<https://www.gps.gov/systems/gps/modernization/>).

8. Global Positioning System (GPS) Application in Precision Agriculture

Global Positioning System (GPS) permits farmers to gather data with accurate location information in real-time. Global Positioning System (GPS) is suitable for the following tasks;

- Mapping of irrigation systems, fields and roads;
- Detection of areas with problem plants
- Soil testing
- VRA (Variable Rate Application) for precise seed and fertilizer application

Needless to say that Global Positioning System (GPS) in agriculture allows for controlling agricultural

machinery
(<https://eos.com/blog/precision-agriculture/>)

Figure 1:An illustration of Global Positioning System (GPS) being used for mapping irrigation systems in a farm.Signals are transmitted to the farm receiver on the farm then calculations are done to determine the exact location.All this is done with the help of a software.

Figure 2:A tractor with parallel steering system.The tractor is fit with a Global Positioning System (GPS) receiver that continuously receives data from satellites.The data received determines the precise location and orientation of the machine in the farm.

8.1.VRT(Variable-Rate Technology) In Precision Agriculture

Variable-Rate Technology (VRT) is a precision farming technique that involves adjusting the application rate of inputs such as fertilizers, pesticides, and seeds to different areas of a field based on their specific needs.VRT(Variable-Rate Technology) uses data from various sources, including satellite

imagery, soil maps, and yield data, to create a customized prescription map that guides the application of inputs to different sections of the field.

By tailoring the input application to the specific needs of each area, VRA can optimize crop yields, reduce input waste, and lower costs, making it an effective and efficient tool for precision farming. There are several kinds of tech that are applied in this area of agriculture. They cover nearly all things such as:

- Hyperspectral Imaging
- Drones
- Artificial intelligence
- Satellites

Nonetheless, the kind of Variable-Rate Technology (VRT) is applied, it is crucial to get to know the general method and how it is used (<https://geopard.tech/blog/variable-rate-application-technology-in-precision-agriculture/>).

According to Earth Observing System Data Analytics, precision agriculture requires a differential global positioning system (DGPS) and specialized software. There are different types of Variable-Rate Technology (VRT) and one of them is map-based Variable-Rate Technology (VRT) which corrects the number of applied fertilizers, pesticides and other products according to the previously generated map. Then there is Sensor-Based Variable-Rate Technology (VRT) which examines the soil with sensors in real-time and can help in determining the nitrogen deficiency. The controlled one determines the number of inputs by estimation.

(<https://eos.com/blog/precision-agriculture/>)

Figure 3: A corn field at the early season is divided into three zones: yellow zones (Zone 2) requires a standard amount of fertilizer, green zones (Higher vegetation) - reduced, red zones (Lower vegetation) - increased.

8.2. Micro Irrigation In Precison Technology

(<https://eos.com/blog/precision-agriculture/>)

Figure 4: The map shows reduced moisture content in plants on the right side of the field (pale purple shades), which may indicate water stress.

8.3. Artificial Intelligence (A.I.) In Precision Agriculture

Machine learning Algorithms are being improved to provide better tools for agricultural management. With the use of computer vision which is a subset of Artificial Intelligence there is early identification of plant related diseases and better crop monitoring when it comes to irrigation. Furthermore, Artificial Intelligence will also assist in how pesticides are being used.

8.4. Internet Of Things In Precision Agriculture

Another important part which Precision Agriculture relies heavily on. Internet Of Things gives farmers the independence to have control of their farms remotely. Case in point Synnefa a Kenyan Startup in AgriTech who are using Internet Of Things to optimize irrigation then connect it to FarmCloud which tracks harvests (<https://www.synnefa.io/>).

8.5. Implications of Proposed Framework

There are different stakeholders proposed in this framework like farmers and policymakers. Some of the key things to be considered are:

- **Investments:**

Set policies which are favourable to investors and that will incentivize them to invest in the country. Subsidies which encourage adoption of farming among the young generation.

- **Infrastructure:**

According to The Kenya Institute For Public Policy Research and Analysis it is estimated that 20 to 30 percent of Kenyan Farmers adopt digital agricultural technologies

(<https://kippra.or.ke/enhancing-market-access-through-digital-technologies-among-smallholder-farmers-in-kenya/>). Enabling access to internet as digital infrastructure is very key in precision agriculture as it relies on internet.

- **Capacity Building among Farmers:**

Capacity building are forums where farmers get trained on certain skills case in point can be digital literacy. Such initiatives reduce the gap which exists among farmers. To add more weight on this one of the things that can be taught is value addition in their products.

Working on the above mentioned items it will create an enabling environment for a successful adoption of precision agriculture in the Global South. All this becomes possible and much easier to accomplish when different stakeholders come and work together. Each and every stakeholder is very key in the cycle.

9. Barriers to Adoption of Precision Technology in the Global South

In as much as precision technology is here to solve agricultural challenges in the Global South, there are limitations when it comes to the adoption of this technology. Some of these challenges include:

- **High up-front acquisition costs** - Acquisition costs for the latest technologies can be prohibitive for farmers with limited resources or access to capital. A feature done by World Bank Group in 2016 says that there are an estimated 500 million smallholder farming households globally, who comprise of a large proportion of the world's poor living on less than \$2 a day. In CGAP's (Consultative Group to Assist the Poor) Smallholder Diaries, researchers met with 270 smallholder farmers in Mozambique, Pakistan, and Tanzania every two weeks for a year to understand their agricultural production, income, and expenses.

(<https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/feature/2016/02/25/a-year-in-the-lives-of-smallholder-farming-families>). This shows how hard it can be when a very expensive technology is implemented and there are limited funds.

•**Farm data sharing and ownership issues** - According to United States Government Accountability Office (U.S GAO) Concerns regarding farm data sharing and ownership can pose obstacles to the widespread use of AI in agriculture. Issues to do with privacy have become very key recently and it shows how sensitive people are to their data more so privacy. Policies are being worked on whereby this issue can be worked on or how we can circumnavigate around it without hurting one another.

•**Low digital literacy skills** - In Kenya there is a lower digital access as a result of low internet penetration which is due to the cost of setting up the infrastructure (World Bank, 2021). In as much as the technology can be deployed with low literacy skills it will not be possible to work with the mentioned technology which is precision technology.

•**Weak policy environment** - Kenyan agricultural policy is well-established, but in some cases has proven counter-effective or poorly enforced. Pro-import trade policies create significant competition for local markets. Mismanagement of government agricultural parastatals results in delays in paying farmers, poor distribution of produce, and lack of storage facilities, among other issues. Poor enforcement of environmental policies has resulted in significant encroachment of forests and wetlands; consequent environmental degradation exacerbates farmers' struggle with climatic volatility. Weak enforcement strategies for existing land policies create significant land tenure insecurity. This is a major contributor to low productivity; long-term investment in land quality is not an effective strategy for farmers who have no tenure to the land (World Bank, 2021).

10. Solutions To The Mentioned Challenges In Regards To Precision Technology In Agriculture

In as much as challenges are posed, there are solutions which when implemented can work.

- **Creating favorable policies that will enable access and growth of this technology** – This is where we need people who understand the nitty gritty of what farmers are going through and what they need. If good policies are set it will make it easier for the growth and penetration of this technology.
- **Enhance access to capital among farmers in the Global South** – Institutions like The World Bank, Consultative Group for International Agricultural Research (CGIAR), United States Agency for International Development (USAID), the African Development Bank, and the Gates Foundation, are major sources of finance for Kenyan digital agriculture. Network operators such as Safaricom, Airtel and Telkom offer general services, including connectivity and mobile money, that are readily applied to the agricultural sector. Other private actors, such as Upande Limited and Twiga, offer agriculture-specific needs (World Bank, 2021).
- **Enhanced Partnership** – Enabling partnerships between the Public and the Private is also another important factor. Engagement of other private-sector actors, such as Apollo and Twiga, will help bring practical digital solutions to stakeholders at economies of scale, and catalyze public sector establishment of nationwide mobile and broadband services. Public-private

partnerships with international public organizations with a focus on pre-competitive research will be particularly helpful in developing strong business models and quickly scaling up innovative digital agriculture solutions (World Bank, 2021).

Conclusion

By and large, precision agriculture powered by artificial intelligence (A.I) holds immense potential to address the challenges faced by the smallholder farmer in the Global South. By providing targeted information since one size does not fit all and leveraging on different technologies we see that there is potential for increased yield and promotion of sustainable farming standards. The proposed framework leverages on affordable and accessible technologies, such as mobile devices and sensors, combined with advanced AI techniques to provide actionable insights for improved farm management. The framework's key components include data collection, data amalgamation and bound compilation, AI-based modeling and analysis, recommendation generation, and propagation via user-friendly interfaces. The framework's unique features, such as its participatory approach, scalability, use of affordable technologies, and region-specific modeling, ensure that the solutions are tailored to the specific needs and contexts of smallholder farmers in the Global South. By empowering farmers with knowledge and tools, the framework aims to create a collaborative and inclusive environment that fosters sustainable agricultural practices. The potential benefits of adopting precision agriculture in the Global South are numerous, including increased crop yields, reduced environmental impact, and improved livelihoods for smallholder farmers. However, several barriers to adoption exist, such as high upfront costs, digital literacy challenges, and weak policy environments. Addressing these barriers through favorable policies, enhanced access to capital, and public-private partnerships is crucial for the successful implementation of precision agriculture in the Global South. The adoption of AI-driven precision agriculture in the Global South has the potential to revolutionize smallholder farming, leading to increased food security, economic empowerment, and sustainable development. By collaborating with various stakeholders and addressing the challenges faced by farmers, we can unlock the transformative power of precision agriculture and create a more resilient and prosperous future for communities in the Global South.

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